

Trust Definitions

Definitions of trust used in the articles

Table 1
Trust definition table

Cod	Definition	Analyze1	Analysis 2	Analyze3
A30	trust in a person is an engagement to an action based on the belief that the future actions of that person will lead to a good result	Based on belief in action	Good results	
A36	Trust is a user's belief about functional reliability and confidence in the system's services.	Based on belief in functionality		
A42	A qualitative or quantitative property of a trustee, evaluated by a Trustor as a measurable belief, subjectively or objectively, for a given task, in a specific context, for a specific period	Qualitative or quantitative of Administrator	Belief-based	According to the context
A37	Trust is defined as the degree of belief that the brand of products provided on the online education site will strive to provide excellent products or services to customers	Belief-based	That the company will offer quality service	
A39	Trust is the level of certainty of reliance toward the confident expectation of something or someone	Based on someone else's expectations		
A35	Virtual team trust has been defined as "the overall willingness of virtual team members to rely on one another that results from the aggregate of potential trust dimensions achieved through socio-emotional and task processes and supported by technological capabilities"	Willingness to accept damages	Based on expectation of intention or behavior	Based on belief in ability
A32	Virtual team trust has been defined as "the general willingness of virtual team members to trust each other that results from the aggregation of potential dimensions of trust achieved through social-emotional and task processes and supported by technological resources";	Willingness to trust team members		
A27	"Affective trust is grounded in reciprocated interpersonal care and concern or emotional bonds. cognitive trust is grounded in individual beliefs about peer reliability and dependability as well as competence."	Beliefs-based		
A24	"Trust 'reflects the willingness of one party to be vulnerable to the actions of another, based on the expectation that this other party will perform a particular action, irrespective of monitoring or control structures'"	Willingness to be vulnerable to the actions of another person	Based on the expectation of an action	Independent of control structures

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Cod	Definition	Analyze 1	Analysis 2	Analyze 3
A28	"trust in a person is an engagement to an action based on the belief that the future actions of that person will lead to a good result"	Commitment to an action	Based on beliefs that actions will lead to good results	
A12	Trust is defined as "the belief that the trustee will act in the best interests of the trustor in a given situation, even when controls are unavailable and it may not be in the trustee's best interests to do so"	Based on the belief that the trustee will act in the best interests of the trustor	Independent of monitoring structures	
A15	"trust is defined as the extent to which an individual has confidence and is willing to interact with someone based on words, actions and decisions of others. "	Willingness to interact		
A20	"Affective trust is based on emotional ties resulting from mutual care and concern; Cognitive trust is based on evaluations formulated by the follower regarding the salient characteristics of the leader, such as reliability integrity, dependability, and competence;"	Based on trustee characteristics		
A17	Trust as "the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the actions of another party based on the expectation that the other party will perform a particular action important to the trustor, irrespective of the ability to monitor or control that other party"	Willingness to be vulnerable to the actions of another person	Based on the expectation of an action	Independent of control structures
A13	An implicit set of beliefs that the other party will behave in a dependent manner and will not take advantage of the situation	Based on belief versus action		
A8	The degree to which a student is willing to rely on the e-learning system and has faith and confidence in the instructor or the educational institution to take appropriate steps that help the student achieve his or her learning objectives.	Willingness to trust the system and system agents	Belief-based	
A7	It is a particular level of subjective probability with which an agent assesses that another agent (or group of agents) will perform a certain action, before the agent can monitor it (or independently of its ability to monitor it) and in a context where it affects your own action.	Action-based	According to the context	Independent of control structures
A6	Trust from a learner's perspective is their willingness to believe and have confidence in a teaching agent so that they take appropriate action to help them achieve their learning objective or intended learning outcome;	Based on belief in the agent's action	Good results	

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Cod	Definition	Analyze 1	Analysis 2	Analyze 3
A1	process that develops over time; A characteristic of collaboration where members believe in each other's character, ability, integrity, familiarity, and morality;	Based on trustee characteristics		
A3	Willingness to depend on others; Trustworthiness, the perception that someone possesses attributes that are beneficial to the trustor;	Willingness to depend on others	Has beneficial attributes	
A44	Team trust has been defined as a psychological state in which team members are willing "to accept vulnerability based on positive expectations from one or more specific individuals"	Willingness to become vulnerable	Based on expectations	
A34	Trust is the user's trust in the application and is part of the perceived benefits of using the application	Based on expectations		
A46	It can be understood as a subjective expectation that an agent has about the behavior of others when they perform an action	Based on expectations	Subjective evaluation	Based on behaviors and actions